

FACTORS INFLUENCING STUDENTS' SUCCESS IN FIRST-YEAR ACCOUNTING MODULES AT A PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION (PHEI) IN GQEBERHA, SOUTH AFRICA

Salaama Parker^{1*}, Kim Van Rooyen²

¹Mrs., IIE Varsity College, SOUTH AFRICA, sparker@varsitycollege.co.za

²Mrs., IIE Varsity College, SOUTH AFRICA, kvanrooyen@varsitycollege.co.za

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

Accounting education in South Africa plays a pivotal role in preparing individuals for careers in finance, business, and various other sectors of the economy. It serves as the foundation upon which future accountants and financial professionals build their knowledge and skills. Students pursuing first-year accounting modules at private higher education institutions (PHEIs) should exhibit a deep understanding of accounting principles, fostering a solid foundation for their future studies and careers. However, students often face challenges that hinder their success. Age-related differences in academic achievement persist, and prior academic achievement varies widely among students. Furthermore, mathematical aptitude is not consistently cultivated to support the quantitative aspects of accounting, peer-to-peer accounting tutorials' impact on academic success is understudied, and not all students may have equal access to adequate support. Given this, the objective of this study is to investigate the factors influencing students' success in first-year accounting modules at a PHEI in Gqeberha, South Africa.

This study employed a quantitative design and included all students who enrolled in the first-year accounting modules at the PHEI during 2023. Data collection involved extracting secondary data from the institution's database and the lecturer's records for the relevant academic year. Specifically, the research focused on four key factors that possibly influence the students' success, namely age, prior academic performance, attendance of peer-to-peer accounting tutorials and previous accounting knowledge. Regression analyses revealed that English positively influenced student success while school mathematics had a negative influence. Furthermore, peer-to-peer tutorials and previous accounting knowledge was not significant to the academic success of the students.

Understanding the factors that influence students' success in accounting education is crucial for educators, institutions, and policymakers to improve the quality of accounting programs and enhance student outcomes. This knowledge can guide efforts to improve retention rates, enhance learning outcomes, and ensure that accounting education remains accessible and equitable for all students. Additionally, the study's findings have broader implications for accounting education in South Africa, contributing to the ongoing discourse on pedagogical practices and student support strategies in the field of accounting.

Keywords: student success, first-year accounting modules, Private Higher Education Institution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Governments allocate substantial resources to universities with expectations centred on student success (Zewotir, North and Murray, 2011). In the case of South Africa, significant budgetary allocations, amounting to R133.8 billion for the 2023/2024 financial year, underscore the government's emphasis on higher education and training (Nzimande, 2023). PHEIs in South Africa have emerged as important contributors to the higher education landscape. They often cater to diverse student populations, including individuals who may not have qualified for admission to public universities or who seek specialized programs and smaller classes. They contribute to increasing access to tertiary education, addressing the growing demand for skilled professionals, including accountants (Council on Higher Education [CHE], 2020). PHEIs accounted for around 8% of the total student enrolment in higher education institutions in 2020 (CHE, 2020).

Within the higher education landscape, accounting education plays a pivotal role in preparing individuals for careers in finance, business, and various sectors of the economy. The Financial Sector Conduct Authority (FSCA) reported that the financial services sector, which relies heavily on accounting expertise, contributed approximately 22% to South Africa's GDP in 2020 (FSCA, 2020). In addition, The South African Institute of Chartered Accountants (SAICA), revealed that as of 2021, there were over 46,000 registered chartered accountants in the country (SAICA, 2021). However, accounting has been identified as a scarce skill crucial for the nation's economic development and it faces a decline in popularity as a high school subject (SAICA, 2008; Schreuder, 2014).

Brook and Roberts, (2021) has considered several factors which might influence academic performance such as: prior academic achievement, gender, age, and numeracy. Mathematics results of students from the age of 16 years has a key impact on their ability to perform at university in accounting courses. (Brook and Roberts, 2021). Papageorgiou and Carpenter, (2019) study indicated that a significant association exists between students' academic performances that had high school accounting compared to students that did not have accounting prior of registering for the accounting course. Furthermore, Ibrahim and Wumba, (2018) study in Nigeria discovered that peer-tutoring was an effective instructional strategy for students in financial accounting compared to the traditional method.

Given the investment made by the government, the classification of accounting as a scarce skill, and the inconclusive results of previous research related to the topic, understanding the factors influencing student success in accounting education becomes imperative. Therefore, the objective of this study is to investigate the factors influencing students' success in first-year accounting modules at a PHEI in Gqeberha, South Africa. This paper will present a literature review related to the topic, the methodology implemented, the empirical results obtained as well as the conclusions drawn from the study.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The sections to follow will deal with the context of accounting education in South Africa, student performance and the factors influencing such performance.

2.1 The context of accounting education in South Africa

The landscape of accounting education in South Africa presents a multifaceted scenario, reflecting both challenges and opportunities. Mkhize, Davids, Danke and Masela (2022) note a concerning trend, with the subject recording one of the lowest national pass rates in Grade 12 in 2020, coupled with a nearly 40% decline in students taking the final accounting examination from 2016 to 2019. The declining interest in high school accounting is acknowledged by the Gauteng Member of the Executive Council for Education, Panyaza Lesufi, who emphasizes that accounting is not a prerequisite for entrance into undergraduate degrees leading to the Chartered Accountant (CA[SA]) designation (SAICA, 2020). This decline poses a threat to the pipeline of potential university students interested in pursuing a career in accounting or related fields, which in turn impacts the supply of scarce skills to the economy.

At tertiary level, the Bachelor of Commerce (BCom) degree with a focus on accounting is governed by the Higher Education Qualification Framework (HEQF) in South Africa (CHE,2021) The primary purpose of the BCom degree is to equip graduates with conceptual understanding, knowledge, theory, skills, methodology and capacity to function effectively in a broad range of commercial, management and research activities (CHE, 2021). The degree aims to provide graduates with values, knowledge, and skills in the core areas of accounting, economics and management (CHE, 2021). The BCom degree emphasizes graduate attributes that extend beyond these core areas, including critical and analytical thinking, problem-solving skills, the

ability to transfer and apply knowledge across diverse contexts, teamwork capabilities, and effective interpersonal and communication skills (CHE, 2021). In addition, graduates are expected to demonstrate responsibility, accountability, ethical judgment, and an awareness of the need for lifelong learning (CHE, 2021). This reflects a commitment to nurturing professionals who exhibit the broader skills necessary for success in a rapidly evolving global landscape.

The core accounting knowledge areas within the BCom degree encompass fundamental principles of accounting, including decision-making processes and the presentation of financial information (CHE, 2021). The curriculum covers the accounting cycle, the double-entry principle, and the interpretation of the accounting equation. Additionally, students gain proficiency in the preparation, analysis, and interpretation of financial statements, recognizing accounting as the foundation for advanced studies in specialized areas such as auditing, finance, management accounting, taxation, and risk management (CHE, 2021). In this nuanced context, it is important to understand students' success in accounting modules.

2.2 Student success in accounting modules

Student success in accounting modules have been investigated in various context and subsequently measured in a variety of ways across studies, reflecting diverse approaches and considerations. Koh and Koh (1999) took a longitudinal approach, measuring performance in the three-year Bachelor of Accounting degree program through the aggregation of examination marks for each subject in each year. This method allows for a detailed assessment of students' academic progress over the entire program. Brook and Roberts (2021) focused on the average mark achieved by students in their first, second, and final years at university as a measure of performance. The emphasis on the final year reflects the importance of this period in determining overall degree classification. Finally, Williams, Dos Reis, and Yu (2022) analyse students' academic performance related to Financial Accounting in each year level of the BCom Accounting degree, with a specific focus on throughput rate. This rate, defined as the number of students who successfully complete each year level and graduate within the minimum required time, provides a holistic perspective on program completion. Holistic, longitudinal approach focussing on each year.

Al-Rashed (2001) introduces two performance measures, overall Grade Point Average (GPA) upon graduation and GPA in all accounting courses upon graduation. These measures aim to distinguish students based on their program-wide and accounting-specific achievements, reflecting real-world considerations such as recruitment and admission into graduate programs. This approach considers the practical implications of students' academic achievements in accounting.

Doran, Bouillon, and Smith (1991) model total examination performance in both Accounting Principles I and II, emphasizing a comprehensive evaluation of students across multiple courses. Lane and Porch (2002) use grade point results for specific modules, such as 'Business Financial Statements' and 'Introduction to Management Accounting,' gathered from university records. Focusing on specific modules provides a targeted evaluation of students' performance in key areas of accounting, allowing for a more granular analysis.

Guney's (2009) study used many dependent variables, including final marks in specific accounting modules and the average of marks of those accounting modules. This multi-variable approach allows for a nuanced understanding of students' performance, considering their achievements in different components of the curriculum. Papageorgiou and Carpenter (2019) categorize students based on pass/fail criteria, with a focus on the final exam marks for first-year accounting. This straightforward approach facilitates a clear distinction between students who pass and fail, providing a binary measure of success.

Critically, the differences in measurement methods across these studies reflect the complex nature of student performance in accounting modules. While some studies adopt a comprehensive approach, considering multiple courses and program-wide achievements, others focus on specific modules or use binary pass/fail criteria. These diverse methods contribute to a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing student success in accounting programs, considering various aspects of academic achievement and program completion.

2.3 Factors influencing students' success in accounting

The success of students in PHEIs is a concern, prompting the need to identify factors influencing academic success.

2.3.1 Age

Age can influence students' approach to learning and their ability to balance academic responsibilities with other life commitments. Furthermore, younger and older students may have different learning styles and preferences, which could impact their performance in accounting courses. The influence of age on students' performance in undergraduate accounting modules has been a subject of contention in academic literature, revealing inconsistent findings. According to Cohn (1972), age is a proxy for maturity and older students tend to be more dedicated to completing course assessments and adopt a more conscientious study approach which leads to higher results. In contrast, Koh and Koh (1999) found that younger students outperformed older students. Bartlett, Peel, and Pendlebury (1993) concur that age has been found to be a substantial contributing factor to performance in an accounting programme, stating that on average, older students achieved lower results in accounting examinations. Other studies find that age has no statistically significant relationship with student performance in an accounting degree programme in the United Kingdom (Gammie, Jones, and Robertson-Millar 2003). Given these contrast findings, the following hypothesis will be tested in this study:

H1: Age significantly influences students' success in first-year accounting modules.

2.3.2 Prior Academic Performance

Admission requirements for a BCom degree in accounting in South Africa emphasize the importance of specific subject performance, including English, Mathematics, and sometimes Accounting (Papageorgiou and Carpenter, 2019). Criteria for these programs vary among universities, requiring applicants to attain specific grades in these subjects. High school academic performance, particularly in Mathematics and English, is often indicative of success in accounting education, acting as a strong predictor (Weisberg, 2018). A solid foundation in these subjects may provide students with an advantage in comprehending accounting concepts and excelling in coursework.

A study in Kuwait, where a GPA score was used to measure academic performance show a strong indication that students who achieve an overall higher GPA score, perform better in undergraduate accounting courses (Eskew and Faley, 1998). Doran et al. (1991) agree that academic aptitude and higher education academic performance are significantly and positively correlated. Brooks and Roberts (2021), further concur, stating that student performance in their early years has a positive impact in performance at university.

Lane and Porph (2015) investigated the correlation between General Certificate of Secondary Education (GCSE) level results and performance in accounting modules for non-specialist students. The findings of this study affirmed that student's performance at GCSE level is a major factor in explaining performance in Level 1 introductory accounting modules for non-specialist students.

The relationship between language proficiency, particularly in English, and academic performance in accounting is a notable aspect. (William Dos Reis and Yu 2022) provide empirical evidence showing a strong correlation between proficiency in English language and Mathematics and students' performance in first-year Accounting.

Moreover, English marks in the final National Senior Certificate (NSC) examination in South Africa are considered predictors of academic performance in accounting degrees (Müller, Prinsloo and du Plessis, 2007; Papageorgiou, 2017). However, South Africa's diverse linguistic landscape, with 11 official languages, adds complexity to this relationship. Papageorgiou (2017) highlights a correlation between students' language backgrounds (English first language, English first additional language, and Afrikaans first additional language) and Accounting 1 performance. In the South African context, learners who are taught in their home language tend to score higher in Mathematics (Howie, 2003). Studies in different contexts, such as Somalia (Addow, Abubakar, and Abukar, 2013) and Pakistan (Ud Din and Saeed, 2018), confirms the complex relationship between English proficiency and performance in accounting by reporting varying degrees of correlation between the two.

In summary, poor English language proficiency may hinder students from decoding accounting concepts outside their daily vocabulary, potentially leading to challenges in applying knowledge to problem-solving (Koch and Kriel, 2005). Therefore, Wong and Chia (1996) recommend that universities explore alternative means of assessing English proficiency to enhance academic performance. In essence, while language proficiency, particularly in English, appears influential in accounting performance, the complexity of linguistic diversity and academic outcomes necessitates more research. Therefore, the following hypothesis will be

tested in this study:

William, Dos Reis and Yu (2022) study concludes that the higher the academic performance achieved in Grade 12 Accounting and Mathematics, the greater the probability to complete the degree in three years. Brook and Roberts, (2021) agree that a basic mathematical aptitude is essential when applying for an undergraduate course in accounting. Therefore, school maths results will be tested as a hypothesis in this study.

H2: High school mathematics and English marks significantly influence students' success in first-year accounting modules.

2.3.3 Attendance of Peer-to-Peer Accounting Tutorials

Engagement in supplementary academic support, such as peer-to-peer accounting tutorials, can enhance students' understanding of course material and improve their chances of success (Tinto, 2012). The research concerned with the relationship between peer-to-peer tutoring and performance in accounting focussed on both secondary and tertiary education. In terms of the research conducted in schools, Olulowo, Ige and Ugwoke (2020) found that peer-to-peer tutoring was more effective than conventional lessons in improving students' academic performance in financial accounting concepts in Nigeria. Using a multiple case study approach in South Africa, de Kock (2021) found that peer-to-peer tutoring increased the academic performance of Grade 8 and 9 accounting learners.

Studies conducted in higher education institutions underscore the positive influence of peer-to-peer tutoring on students' academic performance, particularly in the context of financial accounting and related fields. Ibrahim and Wunba's (2018) research focused on peer-to-peer tutoring in Nigeria, revealing a significant improvement in the average performance of students. Similarly, Fox and Stevenson (2007) explored the impact of peer-to-peer tutoring in Scotland, targeting accounting and finance students. The findings indicated that peer-to-peer tutoring, facilitated by third-year students, positively affected the academic performance of first-year tutees. This suggests that collaborative learning approaches can contribute to better outcomes in financial accounting education. In addition, the development of academic writing skills, study techniques, and examination preparation highlights the multifaceted benefits of peer-to-peer tutoring beyond subject-specific knowledge (Fox & Stevenson 2007). However, in a systematic literature review on peer-to-peer tutoring in tertiary education, Stigmar (2016) argued that university instructors do not universally agree that peer teaching invariably leads to increased academic achievement or profound learning. Instead, they recognize the value of additional pedagogical advantages, such as enhancing students' critical thinking, learning autonomy, motivation, as well as collaborative and communicative skills. Therefore, the following hypothesis will be tested in this study:

H3: Attendance of peer-to-peer accounting tutorials significantly influences students' success in first-year accounting modules.

2.3.4 Previous Accounting Knowledge

Students with prior exposure to accounting concepts, such as those who studied accounting as a high school subject, may have a head start in their first-year accounting module. The impact of prior accounting knowledge on the success in first-year accounting modules remains a topic of interest (Choy & Quek, 2019). The relationship between prior accounting knowledge and student performance is a multifaceted and context-dependent phenomenon, as evidenced by studies conducted in various countries.

In South Africa, accounting marks in the final National Senior Certificate (NSC) examination are considered predictors of academic performance in accounting degrees (Müller et al., 2007; Papageorgiou, 2017). In the United Kingdom, Brook and Roberts (2021) challenged the conventional wisdom that A Level Accounting significantly influences overall academic performance in accounting programs. Despite a positive correlation at Level 4, the subsequent negative trend at Levels 5 and 6, coupled with a lack of statistical significance, raises questions about the sustained impact of prior knowledge. The possibility of student complacency at higher levels and the non-correlation between softer skills and examination results underscore the complexity of factors influencing success.

Meanwhile, in Australia, Hartnett, Römcke, and Yap (2004) established a significant association between accounting study prior to university and student performance, particularly in the first year. However, their finer analysis reveals that the significance diminishes beyond the first year, suggesting that the impact of prior knowledge may be more pronounced in the initial stages of the accounting program. Conversely, the

study conducted in Singapore by Koh and Koh (1999) indicates that prior accounting knowledge is significant in the second and third years of the program, with commerce students performing worse than non-commerce students. The South African studies by Papageorgiou and Carpenter (2019) and Williams, Dos Reis, and Yu (2022) consistently highlight a positive association between prior accounting knowledge and academic success. Papageorgiou and Carpenter (2019) emphasize the influence of school academic performance in accounting and mathematics on the throughput rate, supporting the idea that success in these subjects correlates with degree completion. Williams, Dos Reis, and Yu (2022) further reinforce the significance of academic performance in accounting and mathematics, noting specific grade thresholds for completing the degree in record time and achieving a higher throughput rate.

Collectively, these findings underscore the nuanced and dynamic nature of the relationship between prior accounting knowledge and student performance, emphasizing the need to consider factors such as geographical location, program level, and the specific nuances of the academic context. Therefore, the following hypothesis will be tested in this study:

H4: Previous accounting knowledge significantly impacts students' success in first-year accounting modules.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a positivistic research paradigm and consequently, a quantitative, correlational research design was implemented. This involved the collection and analysis of quantitative data related to students' success in first-year accounting modules at a PHEI in Gqeberha, South Africa. The target population of the study included all students who enrolled in the first-year accounting modules at the PHEI during 2023 (N = 112). The population parameters specified that the participants must be registered first-year BCom students over the age of 18 years, who attended the compulsory accounting modules during 2023.

The sampling frame, which was a list of the target population, was obtained from the PHEI. Since it was possible to collect and analyse data from every member in the population, a census was used in terms of sampling to ensure representativeness and the generalisability of the results. However, 16 of the students had missing data and were excluded from the analysis. Therefore, a sample of 96 usable participants were included in the study. The research utilized secondary data from the institutional database and the lecturer's records for the module. Specifically, the research focused on four key factors that could influence the students' success: age, prior academic performance, attendance of peer-to-peer accounting tutorials and previous accounting knowledge. In addition, the final marks for the two first-year accounting modules were also collected to measure student performance.

The dataset composed of students from various age groups who entered the institution with varying levels of prior academic preparation. The dependent variable for this study was "students' success" in the first-year accounting modules. It was operationalized as the average of the final grades achieved in the 1st and 2nd semester modules. The independent variables were measured as follows:

- Age = students' age at the time of enrolment.
- Prior Academic Performance = high school mathematics and English marks, collected as continuous variables.
- Attendance of Peer-to-Peer Accounting Tutorials = number of sessions that each students attended.
- Previous Accounting Knowledge = marks for high school or Higher Certificate accounting, which is a continuous variable.

The data were anonymized to ensure privacy and confidentiality of the participants. Ethical approval for the use of this data was obtained from the institution's research ethics committee. Regression analyses were employed to assess the impact of the independent variables on students' success. Statistical analyses were conducted using the statistical package Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

4 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Tables 1 and 2 contains the results of the regression analyses performed to test the hypotheses in this study.

Table 1: The influence of Age, School Mathematics, School English and Tutorial attendance on student success

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.519 ^b	.269	.237	14.0741		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6706.555	4	1676.639	8.464	<.001 ^b
	Residual	18223.306	92	198.079		
	Total	24929.861	96			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	31.856	23.033		1.383	.170
	Age	-.445	.879	-.046	-.506	.614
	School Mathematics	-.211	.092	-.210	-2.304	.023
	School English	.867	.168	.473	5.170	<.001
	Tutorial Attendance	.602	.416	.130	1.446	.152

a. Dependent Variable: Student Success
b. Predictors: (Constant), Tutorial Attendance, School Mathematics, School English, Age

Table 1 indicates that the overall regression model was significant ($F(4,92) = 8.464$; $p < .001$) and the independent variables explained 27% of the variance in students' success ($R^2 = 0.269$). However, only 2 of the 4 independent variables had a significant influence on students' success. School English had a significant positive influence on student success ($p < 0.001$; $b^* = 0.473$). However, School mathematics had a significant negative influence on student success ($p < 0.05$; $b^* = -0.210$). The other independent variables, namely age ($p = 0.614$; $b^* = -0.046$) and tutorial attendance ($p = 0.152$; $b^* = 0.130$) did not have a significant influence on student success. Although not statistically significant, it is still interesting to note that age could have a negative influence on students' success. Given the fact that not all students had previous accounting knowledge, a separate regression analysis was performed to test this relationship of which the results can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: The influence of previous accounting knowledge on student success

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.116 ^b	.013	-.011	15.0291		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	125.812	1	125.812	.557	.460 ^b
	Residual	9260.805	41	225.873		
	Total	9386.616	42			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	65.325	8.856		7.376	<.001
	Previous accounting knowledge	.114	.153	.116	.746	.460

a. Dependent Variable: Student Success
b. Predictors: (Constant), Previous accounting knowledge

As can be seen in Table 2 only 42 out of the 96 students had previous accounting knowledge. The results indicate that the regression model was not significant ($F(1,41) = 0.557$; $p = 0.460$) and that previous accounting knowledge only explained 1.3% of the variance in student success ($R^2 = 0.013$). Furthermore, previous accounting knowledge ($p = 0.460$; $b^* = 0.116$) did not have a significant influence on student success.

Given the results of the regression analyses, one of the four hypotheses cannot be rejected. This hypothesis deals with prior academic performance (H^2), however contradictory results were found regarding the direction

of the influences. In terms of school English, a positive influence was found, whereas a negative influence was returned for school mathematics. Furthermore, the hypotheses dealing with age (H^1), tutorial attendance (H^3) and previous accounting knowledge (H^4) were rejected.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The primary objective of the study was to investigate the factors influencing students' success in first-year accounting at a PHEI in Gqeberha, South Africa. This was empirically achieved by testing how age, prior academic performance, peer-to-peer tutorials and prior accounting knowledge influence the academic success of a cohort of students at the PHEI. The regression results revealed that only 2 of the 4 independent variables had a significant influence on student success.

Prior academic performance had an influence on students' success in accounting. The findings reveal that English had a significant positive influence on student success. This implies that English is a significant predictor of academic success, and the better students perform in high school English the more likely they are to succeed in first-year accounting modules. This finding is in line with previous research that showed a strong correlation between English proficiency and student performance in first-year accounting (Williams, Dos Reis and Yu 2022; Müller, Prinsloo and du Plessis, 2007; Papageorgiou, 2017). Clearly, English proficiency is needed for students to understand the accounting principles as indicated by HEQF in South Africa. Because of the complex nature of language in South Africa more detailed research is required. In contrast, school mathematics had a significant negative influence on student success. This indicates that mathematical aptitude is a significant predictor, however its negative influence shows that higher school mathematics marks, does not lead to better student success in first-year accounting modules.

It was found that age does not significantly influence student success in first-year accounting at the PHEI. This is in line with Gammie, Jones, and Robertson-Millar (2003) who found "that age has no statistically significant relationship with student performance in an accounting degree programme in the UK". Age does not seem to be proxy for student maturity or an indication of commitment and the study strategies of students. However, future researchers should look at age, maturity level of the students, the commitment to their studies and study habits used.

Furthermore, the regression analysis revealed that peer-to-peer tutorials was not significant to the academic success of the students. The rejection of the hypothesis challenges the assumption that high-school accounting knowledge consistently provides an advantage and that peer-to-peer support improves academic achievement. Students who attended more tuts did not outperform students that did not attend. The results are not in line with previous studies in school by, Olulowo, Ige and Ugwoke (2020) that found that peer-to-peer tutoring was more effective than conventional lessons in improving students' academic performance in financial accounting concepts in Nigeria. Furthermore, in universities, Ibrahim and Wunba's (2018) research focused on peer-to-peer tutoring in Nigeria, revealing a significant improvement in the mean performance of students. Similarly, Fox and Stevenson (2007) explored the impact of peer-to-peer tutoring in Scotland, targeting accounting and finance students. Their findings indicated that peer-to-peer tutoring, facilitated by third-year students, positively affected the academic performance of first-year tutees. The cohort of students investigated in this study did not benefit from collaborative learning strategies. The findings are in line with Stigmar (2016) who argued that university instructors do not universally believe that peer teaching invariably leads to increased academic achievement or profound learning. Instead, they recognize and value of additional pedagogical advantages, such as enhancing students' critical thinking, learning autonomy, motivation, as well as collaborative and communicative skills. However, future researchers must not only look at marks but also consider the softer skills referred to above. One of the limitations of the study was that the BCom cohort of students was a small sample. Future research should consider a bigger sample and a longitudinal study.

The regression analysis revealed that previous accounting knowledge was not significant to the academic success of the students. The results are in contrast with previous studies of Hartnett, Römcke, and Yap (2004) in Australia who established a significant association between accounting study prior to university and student performance, particularly in the first year. Conversely, the study conducted in Singapore by Koh and Koh (1999) also indicated that prior accounting knowledge is significant in the second and third years of the program, with Commerce students performing worse than non-Commerce students. The South African studies by Papageorgiou and Carpenter (2019) and Williams, Dos Reis, and Yu (2022) also consistently highlight a positive association between prior accounting knowledge and academic success. However, the findings are somewhat in line with studies that indicated a nuanced relationship between prior accounting

knowledge and student success in first year accounting. For example, Brook and Roberts (2021), challenged the conventional wisdom related to previous accounting knowledge when they found a declining influence over the three-year degree programme.

Given the current debate around South Africa for the inclusion of accounting as an admission requirement, this study echoes the sentiments of the Gauteng MEC for Education, who emphasizes that accounting is not a prerequisite for entrance into undergraduate degrees (SAICA - media statement, 2020). It should be noted that the findings of this study could have been influenced by the fact that only a small percentage of students had prior accounting knowledge and that this knowledge was gained either through a higher certificate or National Senior Certificate. Future research should consider a bigger sample and a longitudinal study.

REFERENCE LIST

- Addow, A. M., A. H. Abubakar, and M. S. Abukar. (2013) English language proficiency and academic achievement for undergraduate students in Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2): 59–66.
- Brook, S. and Roberts, M. (2021) What are the determinants of student performance on an undergraduate accounting degree? *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 45(9): 3-8.
- Council on Higher Education. (2021) Higher Education Qualifications Sub-Framework. [Online] Available at: <https://www.che.ac.za/> [Accessed 30 January 2024]
- Dockweiler, R. and Willis, C. (1984) On the use of entry requirements for undergraduate accounting programs, *The Accounting Review*, 59 (3): 496-504.
- Doran, B., Bouillon, M. and Smith, C. (1991) Determinants of student performance in Accounting Principles I and II. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 6(1): 83-84.
- Eskew, R. K. and R. H. Faley. (1988) Some determinants of student performance in the first college-level Financial Accounting course. *Accounting Review*, 63(1): 137–147.
- Financial Sector Conduct Authority. (2020) FSCA About us. [Online] Available at: <https://www.fsca.co.za/> [Accessed 30 January 2024].
- Guney, Y. (2009) Exogenous and endogenous factors influencing students' performance in undergraduate accounting modules. *Accounting Education: An International Journal*, 18(1): 51-73.
- Hartnett, N., Römke, J. and Yap, C. (2004) Student performance in tertiary-level accounting: an international student focus. *Accounting and Finance*, 44(1): 6-10.
- Howie, S. J. (2003) Language and other background factors affecting secondary pupils' performance in Mathematics in South Africa. *African Journal of Research in SMT Education*, 7: 1–20.
- Ibrahim, A. and Wunba, K. G. (2018) Effect of peer-tutoring learning teaching method on academic performance of financial accounting students in Federal Unity Colleges, in North-Eastern Nigeria. *Journal of advanced research in Social Sciences*, 1(1): 7-15.
- Koch, E. and M. Kriel. (2005) An argument for integrating language or language related skills in the accounting curriculum. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 19(3): 219–229.
- Koh, M.Y. and Koh, H.C. (1999) The determinants of performance in an accountancy degree programme. *Accounting Education*, 8(1): 13-29.
- Lane, A. and Porch, M. (2002) The impact of background factors on the performance of nonspecialist undergraduate students on accounting modules – a longitudinal study: a research note. *Accounting Education*, 11(1): 109-118.
- Mkize, T., Davids, M., Danke, S. and Masela, N. (2022) High school accounting at the crossroads: a case study of a township school in Gauteng. *African Perspectives of Research in Teaching & Learning*, 6(1): 105-118.
- Müller, H., P. Prinsloo and A. du Plessis. (2007) Validating the profile of a successful first-year accounting student. *Meditari Accounting Research*, 15(1): 19–33

- Olulowo, T., Ige, O. and Ugwoke, E. (2020) Using peer tutoring to improve students' academic achievement in financial accounting concepts. *Hindawi Education Research International*, 1-10
- Papageorgiou, E. (2017) Accounting students' profile versus academic performance: a five-year analysis. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 31(3): 209-229.
- Papageorgiou, E. and Carpenter, R. (2019) Prior accounting knowledge of first-year students at two South African universities: contributing factor to academic performance or not? *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 33(6): 249-264.
- Rajoo, T. 2012. *An investigation into the role of the Head of Department (HOD) as an instructional leader in the leadership and management of the teaching & learning of accounting in two secondary schools in one district in Gauteng*. Johannesburg: University of the Witwatersrand.
- South Africa Institute of Chartered Accountants. 2021. SAICA, Who we are. [Online] Available at: www.saica.org.za [Accessed 30 January 2024]
- South Africa Institute of Chartered Accountants. 2022. SAICA. Integrated Report 2022. [Online] Available at: *SAICA-Integrated-Report-2022-Digital-Friendly.pdf* (windows.net) [Accessed 30 January 2024]
- South African Government. 2023. Minister Blade Nzimande: Higher Education and Training Department Budget Vote 2023/24. [Online]. Available at: Minister Blade Nzimande: Higher Education and Training Dept Budget Vote 2023/24 | *South African Government (www.gov.za)* [Accessed 30 January 2024]
- Stigmar, M. 2016. Peer-to-peer Teaching in Higher Education: *A Critical Literature Review. Mentoring and Tutoring* 24(2):124-136
- Ud din, K. and M. Saeed. 2018. "Relationship between university students' English proficiency, academic achievement and their satisfaction on teacher feedback." *Bulletin of Education and Research* 40(3): 129-143
- Williams, B, dos Reis, K and Yu, D. 2022. Exploring the influence of students' matric accounting knowledge on the successful completion of a Bcom accounting mainstream degree: a comparative study at a university in the western cape. *South African Journal of Higher Education*. 36(2) 280-296
- Wong, D. S. N., & Chia, Y. M. (1996). English language, mathematics, and first-year financial accounting performance: *a research note. Accounting Education*, 5(2), 183-139.